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DEVELOPING AN APPLICATION TO GATHER AND CENTRALIZE THE INFORMATION OBTAINED FROM THE INNOVATION COMPETENCIES ASSESSMENT IN MASSIVE PROJECT-BASED COURSES

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ABSTRACT

Today innovation is essential in any country that aims to increase its economic growth and the welfare of its population. Therefore, organizations need to innovate and provide meaningful solutions to their customers to succeed in an ever-changing business ecosystem. It implies that their collaborators must be capable to manage and implement innovation. Consequently, engineering schools are facing the challenge to provide capable engineers in this matter to the job market to satisfy organizations and society needs. Motivated by the need to develop in engineering students the capability to lead and perform innovation successfully, it is critical to understand how to perform the teaching process in a way to ensure proficiency in innovation at the end of the study programs. A project was started to understand which methodologies support the development of competencies associated with the probability to produce innovations. Based on the literature and the innovation track curriculum, three competencies were chosen to be assessed; critical thinking, teamwork, and communication. After implementing the first course of the innovation track several difficulties were found. The teachings staff set a group of actions to close the detected gaps. In order to implement them, it was recognized the need to develop an application to gather and centralize the information obtained from the assessment process.

The main characteristics of this application are described, and its benefits are discussed. This application will enable engineering schools to establish a data-based decision-making process to implement a continuous improvement philosophy in the organization.

1. INTRODUCTION

Today innovation is essential in any country that aims to increase its economic growth and the welfare of its population (OECD, 2012). As an example, the European Commission, in order to invigorate the European economy, has put the innovation policy as a central element (Fagerber and Verspagen, 2009). At the same time companies are concerned about their ability to innovate, and they are aware of its importance for their future (Christensen, 1997; Christensen and Raynor 2003).

Considering this fact and the need of organizations to innovate and provide meaningful solutions to their customers to succeed in an ever-changing business ecosystem, it is necessary that their collaborators be capable to manage and implement innovation. Therefore, engineering schools are facing the challenge to provide capable engineers in this matter to the job market to satisfy organizations and society needs. Considering the need to develop in engineering students the capability to lead and perform innovation successfully, it is very important to implement the assessment cycle in a way that ensures the development of the competencies related to innovation at the end of the study program. In this article, the case of an application to gather and centralize information, resulting from the innovation competencies assessment, will be treated. The application purpose is closing the gaps detected during the implementation of the new engineering and sciences track curriculum in the year 2019. This year, the first of three project-based courses, with a specific focus on developing competencies that correlate positively with the possibility to implement innovation, was implemented. The first course must be taken by 900 freshmen students in 9 sections of 100 students each.

The first part of the document introduces the theoretical background that supports the competencies selected to be assessed in these courses. Secondly, the competencies assessment process is explained. Thirdly, the first course of the track is explained as well as its improvement opportunities related to assessment. Finally, the design and implementation plan to improve the course assessment process, based on the application, is discussed.

2. THE INNOVATION COMPETENCES

One of the concepts that today is capturing the attention of companies around the globe is innovation. As a matter of fact, innovation is becoming a central part of the efforts of companies to stay ahead in their business and ensure their subsistence in the future (Christensen, 1997; Christensen and Raynor, 2003). At the same time countries are increasingly caring about this topic because they have understood that it is one way to ensure economic growth and social development (Faberge and Verspagen, 2009; OECD, 2011). A clear example is the fact that the European Commission has recognized that higher education institutions are not contributing as much as they should to innovation in the wider economy. In addition, the performance varies between EU regions (Laura-Maija, Lindfors, Taatila, 2017). Also, scholars are increasing their interest on the topic, data show a considerable number of publications since the early '90s (Faberge and Verspagen, 2009). In addition, more than 100 centers or departments are doing research on innovation, most of them located in Europe (Faberge and Verspagen, 2009). This evidence supports the idea of developing the innovation competence in engineering students, mainly because they will work in an industry where innovation is a core feature for organizations to survive and grow in an ever-changing market, and these organizations will contribute to countries' growth.

Before continuing our discussion, it is relevant to explain the definition of innovation. Early definitions date from the late 1880s, however the most influential precursor of this concept was the economist Joseph Schumpeter (Sledzik, 2013). Schumpeter defined innovation as “process of industrial mutation, that incessantly revolutionizes the economic structure from within, incessantly destroying the old one, incessantly creating a new one”. Many definitions of innovation have been created in the last decades, however, a broadly accepted definition by scholars is the one proposed by Amabile, who defines innovation as the successful implementation of creative ideas within an organization (Amabile, 2016). In this definition, creativity is considered as part of the process of innovation, as a matter of fact, creativity is defined as the production of novel and useful ideas by an individual or a group of individuals working together (Amabile, 2016). In this line Miron, Erez, and Naveh (2004) state that the implementation of creative ideas leads to innovation. In addition, it is relevant to notice that both are grounded in the assumption that creativity and innovation are subjective constructs, socially bound by historical time and place, and perceptions of usefulness likely vary even within a given domain at a given time (Amabile, 1982,1983).

According to the Dynamic Componential Model of Creativity and Innovation (Amabile, 2016), one of the most recognized models to explain innovation in organizations, innovation is explained at the organizational level, and in its process requires the generation of ideas that emerge from the individual or small group creativity. In this creative process, three elements are fundamental to the process to occur, these are; intrinsic and synergistic extrinsic motivation, skills in the task domain, and creativity-relevant processes. In the modern definitions of innovation, we find two concepts that are included almost in every definition of innovation, novelty, and usefulness. In this model, Amabile (2016) states that organizational innovation is fed by individual/group creativity to produce ideas. At individual or small group level creativity is influenced by the intrinsic motivation, the skills in the task domain and creativity-relevant processes.

After understanding the basics of the innovation concept, it is important to understand how the competence concept has been defined. In the literature, competence represents a set of skills especially as it is applied to a task or a set of tasks (Dej, 2007). In a more complete definition, the concept competence (plural competencies) identifies both the combination of related traits, knowledge, values, attitudes, skills, and abilities embedded in determined context and process of development of them as an integrative construct (Edwards-Schachter et al., 2015). In the same line, the individual innovation competence is understood as a synonym for a set of personal characteristics, knowledge, skills, (or abilities) and attitudes that are connected to creating concretized and implemented novelties via collaboration in complex innovation processes (Laura-Maija, Lindfors, Taatila, 2017). From the previous definitions, it is possible to infer that innovation competence involves several complex elements that present a relevant challenge from the teaching and assessment perspective.

Continuing in the line to enlighten the comprehension of the innovation competence, the literature suggests that innovation competence is a composition of multiple factors and or sub-competencies that could predict innovation to occur if they are present at the individual and/or organizational level.

Regarding the state of the art of innovation competence, it is required to analyze how it can be assessed. According to Butter and Van Beest (2017) Universities do not have tools to measure the development of students' innovation competencies during their studies. Therefore, we do not actually know what teaching and learning methods are effective from the perspective of enhancing innovation competencies. Universities and companies need new reliable and valid tools for innovation competence assessment that could be used throughout the young innovators' path from university to working life in organizations. This statement coincides with the literature review performed for this document, showing the need to perform research in this area based on quantitative methods and develop reliable tools for the assessment process.

Butter and Van Beest (2017) carried out a study to validate the Fincoda model proposed by Marin-Garcia et al. (2016), which proposed creativity, critical thinking, and a cluster of capacities composed by initiative, teamwork, and networking as predictors of innovation.

Creativity: The ability to think beyond existing ideas, rules, patterns or relationships. To generate or adapt meaningful alternatives, ideas, products, methods or services regardless of possible practicality and future added value.

Critical thinking: The ability to analyze and evaluate the advantages and disadvantages and estimate the risks involved for a purpose.

Initiative: The ability to influence/make decisions that foster positive changes. To influence creative people and those who have to implement the ideas.

Teamwork: The ability to work effectively with others in a group.

Networking: The ability to involve external/outside stakeholders outside the team.

In the results of the research was found that relevant innovation process competencies can be measured in an adequate manner. Also, the criterion (creativity, critical thinking, initiative, teamwork, and networking) validity seems satisfactory. The FINCODA dimensions are positively and significantly related to all three types of criterion measured. These are 1) self-ratings of innovative behavior, 2) supervisor ratings of innovative behavior, and 3) real-life examples of innovative

behavior. Also, FINCODA shows incremental validity above general personality. The analyses consistently show that showing initiative is the most determinant of being a successful participant in the innovation process and innovation teams, in the sense that this competency adds predictive power above background variables and personality in predicting innovation behavior (Butter and Van Beest, 2017). However, there are some limitations and needs for further research. An important distinction, that is remarked by Butter and Van Beest (2017), is the need to make differentiated analyses for different educational programs and countries. As an example, it is proposed to study the difference between technical and social work domain students.

In the context of the design of the innovation track and based on the curricular design and the results indicated above, three competencies were chosen to be developed in three innovation courses of the new curriculum. These were critical thinking, teamwork, and communication.

3. COMPETENCIES ASSESSMENT

The competence-based model was implemented in the engineering faculty in 2019. This decision was taken because this model, as Villa and Poblete state (2008), *provides greater enrichment of learning methodologies, closer monitoring, and tutoring of students individually and in a group as well as a range of techniques for assessing learning*. In this model implementation, exists a focus on formative assessment following the recommendation indicated by UD (2006) *The course assessment system must include not only aspects related to final exams before issuing final grades but also includes everything concerned with the formative assessment*.

Assessment by competence means first knowing what we want to evaluate, second explicitly defining how it is going to be evaluated, and third specifying the level of achievement for the course. The teaching staff implemented this approach when designed the assessment system in the first course in the innovation track.

In the implementation, the teaching staff applies strategies such as observation techniques, self-evaluation, and attitude scales for teamwork assessment. On the other hand, the teaching staff applies strategies such as writing essays, the application of knowledge to specific situations, and the development of different types of thinking (analysis, synthesis, comparison, critical, creative, comparative, deliberative, etc.) to assess communication and critical thinking respectively. Finally, the teaching staff inserted all these assessment strategies in the innovation process experienced by the students in the course project.

3.1 Critical thinking

Critical thinking plays a relevant role in innovation, Marin-Garcia et al. (2016) define critical thinking as the ability to analyze issues, evaluate advantages and disadvantages, and estimate the risks involved for a purpose.

Villa and Poblete (2008) state that to develop critical thinking it is required to create situations where assumptions can be examined and checked against others. The object of the analysis will always be our own and others' discourse and actions either directly expressed or observed or else gleaned from written documents or audiovisual content. According to Bhutta et al (2019), a large number of methods ranging from standard tests to more performance-oriented, authentic open-ended techniques such as interviews and portfolios, have been developed and validated to assess critical thinking. In the context of this article, the approach indicated by Bhutta et al. (2019) in which the development of the 'Assessment of Critical Thinking' (ACT) rubric consist of four interlinked phases: (i) identifying main elements of CT; (ii) deciding on the CT rubric format; (iii) adapting CT assessment rubric; as well as, (iv) field-testing and establishing reliability was implemented by the teaching staff. They, after revising the learning outcomes of the course, and based on what Pascarella and Terenzini (1991) state; "critical thinking can be defined in several ways, but typically involves the individual's ability to do some or all of the following: identify central issues and assumptions in an argument, recognize important relationships, make correct inferences from data, deduce conclusions from the information or data provided, interpret whether conclusions are warranted based on the data given, and evaluate evidence or authority", created a list of indicators associated with critical thinking in the context of the course project. Finally, a rubric was developed and implemented in the course evaluation milestones. The rubric is in Appendix A.

3.2 Teamwork

Innovation literature and industry requirements remark the importance of teamwork as a key competence to succeed during the innovation process at the organizational and small team level (Amabile, 2016). In the context of innovation competences, Marin Garcia et al. (2016) define teamwork as the ability to work effectively with others in a group. In a complementary and more detailed perspective, De Los Rios et al. (2012) define teamwork competence as a set of actions, strategies, procedures, and methodologies used by a group of people to achieve objectives and/or goals, sharing responsibilities. Teamwork involves group creation where people meet, collaborate, and interact specifically for a particular purpose (work or project), covering three main lines of action: team building, teamwork, and group dynamics.

Regarding evaluation, the methodology implemented in the course implies an initial activity in which the teams elaborate a contract in which each member of the team sets his/her expectations concerning the other members' performance in aspects such as; obligations and agreements commitment, respect to others, organization, and tasks accomplishment. Then, the students perform a 360-behavior assessment

between teammates through a questionnaire where they evaluate each other in the aspects agreed in the contract. After that, they make an individual evaluation, using a self-assessment survey, and write an individual reflection on their performance. It occurs two times in the semester, in week 9 and week 15. The teaching staff designed the rubrics for teamwork competence assessment, they are shown in Appendix A.

3.3 Communication

The professional and academic communication competence is defined as: Analytically read and listen to different types of relevant texts for the student learning process. Likewise, express in an effective, clear, and informed way his/her ideas, in academic situations, both in oral as in written modality in the Spanish language (FCFM, 2018). Therefore, two dimensions must be assessed in the course by the teaching staff; oral communication and written communication.

Written communication involves the ability to effectively convey multiple types of messages, in multiple forms, to varying audiences, through a written medium (Markle et al., 2013). On the other hand, oral communication is defined as expressing clearly and opportunely one's ideas, knowledge, and feelings in speech, adapting to the audience and, situations to ensure good comprehension and attention (Villa and Poblete, 2008).

The evidence to assess oral communication is collected by the teaching staff from the project presentations in weeks 8 and 15. On the other hand, the written communication evidence is gathered by the teaching staff in the reports delivered by students in weeks 8 and 15. To create an assessment tool for oral and written communication, the teaching staff review the levels and descriptors proposed by Villa and Poblete (2008) and adjusted them according to the curricular design learning goals. The results of this process are shown in the rubric in Appendix A.

4. COURSE DESCRIPTION

The new engineering curriculum, implemented in the year 2019, integrates the development of innovation competence as a fundamental learning goal. Three courses were designated to develop this competence in the innovation track, these are; innovation challenge (1st semester), innovation project (2nd semester), and interdisciplinary module (4th semester). The stem of these courses is an innovation project, framed into the United Nations Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs). The final deliverable is a prototype of the solution.

The three courses have the aim to develop three sub-competencies associated with innovation; critical thinking, teamwork, and communication. These competencies are developed progressively in three levels of authenticity and difficulty. Concerning assessment, each course has two evaluation milestones (summative), the first in

week 8, and the final in week 15. Also, the course has formative assessment instances. Each of these has an individual component and a group component.

In this article, the focus is on the case of the first course called innovation challenge. The formative and summative assessment instances for this course are listed and briefly described in Appendix B.

The indicators associated with the course innovation challenge, for critical thinking, teamwork, and communication are described in detail in Appendix D.

The teaching staff based on the indicators in Appendix D, developed the rubrics for the course for teamwork, communication and critical thinking (part of innovation). The results are show in Appendix A.

Each course receives 900 students per semester distributed in 9 sections of 100 students each. In these sections, the students are divided into 20 groups of 5 members to work on the course project. The teaching staff consists of two engineering teachers, two design teachers, and two final years students.

5. COURSE IMPLEMENTATION DIFFICULTIES AND IMPROVEMENT OPPORTUNITIES

After teaching the first course in 2019, several obstacles and improvement opportunities were identified. To gather the opinions of the teaching staff, a survey to detect the most impactful difficulties was carried out. The results showed that the most relevant obstacles during the implementation of the two courses were; a high number of hours spent on processing the information coming from each assessment milestone, post assessment feedback is delivered late to the students, the assessment information stays contained in separate files that make it difficult to perform further analyses, the information granularity does not allow the team to perform detailed analyses to improve the course performance.

These difficulties impact directly on the competencies development for some students. Considering this, the teaching staff defined four strategic goals to focus its work; improving the time to process the data from the assessment process, registering all the assessment activities per student in the three courses, ensuring the accessibility, quality, and granularity of the data acquired during the assessment process, and performing analyses that contribute to implement a data-based decision-making process in the innovation track to ensure achievement of the competencies defined in the curriculum.

After defining the strategic goals, the teaching staff determined a series of specific actions to close the identified gaps. The specific activities and their objectives are listed in table 1.

Table 1. Strategic goals and associated actions

Strategic goal	Objective	Action
Improve the time to process the data from the assessment process.	Reduce the time to provide prompt feedback to students.	Implement an easy access web database management system.
Register all the assessment activities per student in the three courses.	Centralize and facilitate access to assessment information.	Create a web-based platform to manage centrally all the information gathered from the assessment process.
Ensure the accessibility, quality, and granularity of the data acquired during the assessment process in one database.	Increase the capability to perform analyses to establish a data-based decision-making philosophy in the innovation track.	Create a web-based application to store and manage the data from the assessment process.
Perform analyses that contribute to implement a data-based decision-making process in the innovation track to ensure achievement of the competencies defined in the curriculum.	Ensure the development of the three competencies to be developed in the course; critical thinking, communication, and teamwork.	Implement analysis tools in the web-based applications to perform analysis.

As a result of the activities indicated in table 1 the decision of creating a web-based application to manage all the information coming from the assessment milestones of the three courses was taken. In the next section, the description of the features defined during the design phase will be explained.

5.1- Web-based assessment tool design feature

The basic actions to comply with the course, formative and summative, are detailed in Appendix C. A graphical description of them is shown in figure 1. In this figure, it is noticeable the number of interactions that are needed to gather the evidence in the assessment process. Also, it is remarkable the complexity for the teaching staff to manage the evidence when it must deal with many students.

Figure 1

In Appendix E the cycle for the two types of interactions in the process are described in detail.

Several features and their objectives were defined to be included in the first application prototype during the design phase. These are: implementing the competency assessment rubrics in the web-based application to facilitate the assessment process, implementing a database that connects information that characterizes student (gender, age, city, etc.) with the rubrics to centralize and facilitate access to assessment information, including in the application a dashboard that allows teaching staff to see the achievement level per indicator and its associated learning outcome including filters such as student gender, age, course section, teachers, date of the evaluation, etc. to increase the capability to perform analyses to establish a data-based decision-making philosophy, and creating a virtual portfolio for each student, where he/she can review his/her achievements and the projects in that he/she participated to increase student awareness on his/her performance to promote his/her reflection on his/her learning process.

In the next phase, a team conformed by the course's teachers, educational experts, and application developers will be put in place to initiate the detailed design and implementation phase. A process to capture best practices and lessons learned will be implemented. These outcomes are expected to be communicated in a future article describing the challenges associated with the detailed design, implementation and testing phase.

6. FUTURE RESEARCH

Once the implementation of the web-based innovation competencies assessment tool is finished, several research topics can be developed. The teaching staff determined to define four topics to be researched in order to focalize the resources involved in this project. The first topic is the validation of the impact of the tool in the development of the competencies associated with innovation. The second research topic is understanding the reduction of the time dedicated to performing the assessment process. The third topic is assessing the quality of the data obtained using this tool, and finally, a full-scale implementation will be performed to determine the impact of these three variables in three courses. In this process is recognized the need to work interdisciplinarity including professionals from with educational research background, software and application developers, and engineering and design professionals with an innovation background.

7. CONCLUSIONS

During the creation of a strategy to assess innovation competencies development, in massive project-based courses, the need to implement a web-based application has been recognized by the teaching staff. This application requires the integration of several features that were detected during the courses' implementation by the team. The reasons that justify this effort are related to operational aspects of the course and research opportunities originated in the massive quantity of information gathered during course execution. The most relevant operational aspects to improve are: reducing the number of hours spent on processing the information coming from each assessment, reducing the time to provide feedback to students, integrating the information obtained from the assessment process in a system able to manage it easily, and increase the information detail to allow the teaching staff to perform further analyses. Regarding research opportunities, the most relevant are; validating the impact of some class activities in the development of the competences, comparing the development of the competences between groups of students such as gender, previous background, etc., and validating the contribution of the innovation track model to the development teamwork, communication, and critical thinking. In the design phase, the teaching staff defined attributes that the application has to offer to its users. The actions to include this features are the following: providing the capacity to create or upload the rubrics in the application, implementing a database able to centralize and store the information from the assessment process in each course of the innovation track, creating an online portfolio where he/she can review his/her achievements and the projects in that he/she participated, creating a dashboard to present graphically the results of students' learning process regarding competence development. In this project, it has been detected the relevance of implementing data management tools to guarantee an easy and effective administration of the information resulting from the assessment

process. There are still challenges related to the effective implementation of the application in the course. Most of this challenge is related to the willingness of the teaching staff to adopt this technology in their duties, this implies providing the resources to properly understand the students and teaching staff needs regarding interface design and user experience. Finally, the benefit of this implementation will allow faculty to understand the real impact of the activities in the courses' program to achieve the levels established for each of the competences defined in the curriculum and install a data-based decision-making philosophy to manage the innovation track.

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Appendix A: Course Rubrics

FINAL REPORT RUBRIC					
Written and oral communication descriptors					
Indicators	Excellent 3 points	Very Good 2 points	Good 1 point	Poor 0 points	Total points
Conveying important information (*)	Noteworthy for the clarity in speech of reasoning and/or feelings.	Express well-reasoned ideas.	Present some ideas.	Expresses self poorly or confusedly.	
Controlling nerves sufficiently to express self in public (*)	Expresses self with ease and noteworthy proficiency.	Expresses self with a certain tranquility.	Speaks but it noticeably nervous and ill at ease.	Can't speak due to nerves; gets blocked.	
Field questions (*)	Responds well and easily to the questions that she/he is asked.	Knows how to respond to the questions that she/he is asked.	Responds to the questions that she/he is asked without actually answering them.	Doesn't know how to respond to the questions that she/he is asked.	
Visual aid: Formal aspects of infographic structure title, body, source, credits	The infographic is presented in the format and with all the requested aspects correctly elaborated and are consistent.	The infographic is presented in the format and with the majority (70%) of the requested aspects correctly prepared.	The infographic is presented in the format and with half of the requested aspects correctly prepared.	The infographic neglects the formal aspects, more than half of the requested aspects are absent.	
Visual aid: Text and visual resources relationship	All visual resources (images, tables, graphics) comply with the formal aspects of this type of resource and facilitate understanding.	Most of the visual resources (images, tables, graphics) comply with the formal aspects and allow understanding.	Not all visual resources are formally adequate, making it difficult to understand the message.	Visual resources are not formally adequate and impede understanding of the message.	
	The infographic texts are organized in a balanced way, use correct sentences and images (tables, charts), and suit the context of the final presentation.	The infographic does not present all the relevant information regarding the topic covered in the final presentation.	The infographic presents an overload of textual information and scarce visual resources. Or an excess of visual information and little textual information. The infographic becomes monotonous.	There is information overload and absence of visual resources. Or there is no textual information and excessive visual information. The infographic becomes monotonous.	

Appendix A: Course Rubrics

Written and oral communication descriptors					Total points
Indicators	Excellent 3 points	Very Good 2 points	Good 1 point	Poor 0 points	
Report writing: Formal writing and bibliographic sources	Correctly apply the citation rules (APA). The writing and spelling of the text are adequate, allowing an understanding of the writing.	Correctly apply the citation rules (APA). It presents small inaccuracies in the writing or spelling, but this does not prevent the understanding of the writing.	Applies with some inaccuracies the citation rules (APA). Writing and spelling errors appear, which make the writing difficult to understand.	The citation rules (APA) are not applied correctly, or it does not present it. Errors and mistakes in spelling and writing are abundant, impeding the understanding of the writing.	
Clearly expressing ideas, knowledge, or feelings (*)	Organizes the report sections and paragraphs.	Presents the different aspects of the topic in logical order.	Expression can be understood but the report is disorganized.	Uses confused, hazy, expressions. Very difficult to follow.	
Writing well grammatically (*)	Utilizes prepositions and conjunctions well.	The report is correct as far as spelling and syntax are concerned.	Make spelling mistakes.	Omits subjects or verbs. Uses wrong mood, tense or persons in verbs.	
Using appropriate language for the type of document and reader (*)	Uses synonymous to clarify ambiguous or equivocal terms.	Suits language to the type of document and reader.	Uses the terminology of the subject incorrectly.	Uses own abbreviations or jargon.	
Using appropriate devices to facilitate reading and comprehension of the report (*)	Clearly identifies the essay and its key elements.	Appropriately uses typographic devices (font, paragraph, style formats, etc.)	Overuses formatting devices, hindering comprehension.	Doesn't use typographic devices (font, paragraph, style formats, etc.). Doesn't number pages.	

(*) Indicators and descriptors taken from Villa and Poblete (2008).

Appendix A: Course Rubrics

Innovation (Critical thinking)					Total points
Indicators	Excellent 3 points	Very Good 2 points	Good 1 point	Poor 0 points	
Describing findings and observations	The student describes the most important findings or observations related to the problem to be solved.	The student describes the findings and observations, which are related to the problem to be solved, but are not the most important.	The student describes observations that are not directly related to the problem to be solved.	The student does not present findings, or the observations have no relation to the problem.	
Describing the user	The student describes properly the user and his/her most distinctive characteristics.	The student describes the user and only one of his/her distinctive characteristics.	The student poorly describes the user or does not describe his/her distinctive characteristics.	The student does not describe the user or does not describe his/her distinctive characteristics.	
Describing the problem	The definition of the problem to be solved is consistent with the user and the main findings.	The definition of the problem to be solved is consistent with the user or the main findings.	The definition of the problem is weakly related to the user needs or the main findings.	The definition of the problem is not related to the user needs or the main findings.	
Listing the objectives of the project	The objectives of the project are related to solving the problem.	At least one objective of the project is presented, and it is related to solving the problem.	The objectives of the project are weakly related to solving the problem.	No objectives are presented.	
Presenting the proposed solution at conceptual level	The student shows the proposed solution, using the syntax indicated in the course: What is it? (name that defines it) + For whom? (user) + How? (concept of solution and general operation)	The student shows the proposed solution, using the syntax indicated in the course, although there are inaccuracies.	The student shows the proposed solution, but it does not comply with the syntax indicated in the course.	The student does not show the proposed solution.	

Appendix A: Course Rubrics

Innovation (Critical thinking)					
Indicators	Excellent 3 points	Very Good 2 points	Good 1 point	Poor 0 points	Total points
Presenting a pertinent solution to the user's problem	The student describes the proposed solution, and this is consistent with the user, with the defined problem and its objectives. The details of the innovation and the attributes that characterize it must be described.	The student describes the proposed solution, and this is consistent with the user, or with the defined problem or its objectives. The details of the innovation and the attributes that characterize it are partially described.	The student describes the proposed solution, and this is weakly consistent with the user, or with the defined problem or its objectives. The details of the innovation and the attributes that characterize it are partially described.	The student describes the proposed solution, and this is not consistent with the user, nor with the defined problem nor its objectives. The details of the innovation and the attributes that characterize it are not described.	
Critical analysis of the Project	The student reflects on the project carried out, highlighting the beneficiaries of the solution and those affected. The student reflects on the potential resolution of the problem and its future feasibility.	The student partially reflects on the project carried out, highlighting the beneficiaries of the solution and those affected. The student partially reflects on the potential resolution of the problem and its future feasibility.	The student reflects only on one of the aspects requested by the teaching staff.	The student does not reflect on the aspects requested by the teaching staff.	

Teamwork-Self assessment					
Indicators	Excellent 3 points	Very Good 2 points	Good 1 point	Poor 0 points	Total points
I performed the tasks assigned to me / by the group within the required deadlines	I fulfilled the assigned tasks in the required terms, my contribution was remarkable to the team, and my work facilitated other members work.	I fulfilled the assigned tasks in the required terms, my contribution was not remarkable to the team, and my work partially facilitated other members work.	I partially fulfilled the assigned tasks and didn't fulfilled the scheduled activities.	I didn't fulfilled the assigned tasks.	

Appendix A: Course Rubrics

<p>I participated actively in the team meeting spaces, sharing information, knowledge and experiences.</p>	<p>I was active and participative in the group meetings. With my interventions I encouraged participation and improved the quality of the team's results. My contributions were fundamental both for the group process and for the quality of the result.</p>	<p>I was active and participative in the group meetings. With my interventions I neither encouraged participation nor improved the quality of the team's results.</p>	<p>I was seldom active and participative in the group meetings. With my interventions I neither encouraged participation nor improved the quality of the team's results.</p>	<p>I was not active and participative in the group meetings. I was neither active nor participative in the group meetings.</p>	
<p>I took (took) into account the points of view of others and I provide feedback constructively.</p>	<p>I accepted the opinions of others and I gave my point of view in a constructive way. I encouraged constructive dialogue and inspired participation from other group members. I integrated the opinions of others maintaining a climate of collaboration and support.</p>	<p>I often accepted the opinions of others and I gave my point of view in a constructive way. I often encouraged constructive dialogue and inspired participation from other group members.</p>	<p>I seldom accepted the opinions of others and I gave my point of view in a constructive way. I seldom encouraged constructive dialogue and inspired participation from other group members.</p>	<p>I never accepted the opinions of others and I gave my point of view in a constructive way. I never encouraged constructive dialogue and inspired participation from other group members.</p>	

Appendix C: Course activities and assessment milestones

Week	Class objective	Student deliverable	Group or individual activity	Type of assessment	Assessed competence	Grade %
1	Course presentation	-	-	-	-	-
2	Introduction to SDGs	-	-	-	-	-
3	Community observation, Part 1	Report, observation findings.	Individual	Formative	Critical thinking	-
4	Observation findings, interpretation	Report, findings interpretation.	Teamwork	Formative	Critical thinking	-
5	Community observation, Part 2	Report, observations finding.	Teamwork	Formative	Critical thinking	-
6	Problem definition based on observations	Problem statement and its evidence.	Teamwork	Formative	Critical thinking	-
7	Understanding the user and reframing the problem	Report, reframing the problem.	Teamwork	Formative	Critical thinking	-
8	Intermediate presentation	Oral presentation and report including process evidence and problem statement.	Individual and Teamwork	Summative	Oral and written communication, critical thinking	40% of final grade
9	Feedback session	Peer and self - assessment.	Individual and teamwork	Formative	Teamwork	-
10	Conceptualization and idea generation	-	-	-	-	-
11	Conceptualization and idea generation	Drawings, sketches.	Teamwork	Formative	Critical thinking	-
12	Idea selection and validation	-	-	-	-	-
13	Idea selection and validation	Selection matrix, surveys to potential users, low-resolution prototype.	Teamwork	Formative	Critical thinking	-
14	Final presentation preparation	-	Individual and Teamwork	-	-	-

Appendix C: Course activities and assessment milestones

Week	Class objective	Student deliverable	Group or individual activity	Type of assessment	Assessed competence	Grade %
15	Final presentation	Oral presentation, and report including process evidence, problem statement, generated ideas, selection matrix, surveys to potential users, analysis, low-resolution prototype, and peer and self-assessment.		Summative	Oral and written communication, critical thinking, teamwork	60% of final grade

Appendix C: Assessment activities per week

Act.	Wk 1	Wk 2	Wk 3	Wk 4	Wk 5	Wk 6
Student actions	None	None	Action 1.1: Student uploads observation findings report. Word file.	Action 2.1: Student uploads observation findings interpretation report. Word file.	Action 3.1: Student uploads observation findings interpretation report. Word File.	Action 4.1: Student uploads problem statement and its evidence. Word file.
Teaching staff actions	None	None	None	Action 1.2: Teaching staff uploads observation findings report feedback. Word file.	Action 2.2: Teaching staff uploads observation findings interpretation report feedback. Word file.	Action 3.2: Teaching staff uploads observation findings interpretation report feedback. Word file.
Act.	Wk 7	Wk 8	Wk 9	Wk 10	Wk 11	Wk12
Student actions	Action 5.1: Student uploads report, reframing the problem. Word file.	Action 6.1: Student uploads oral presentation video and intermediate report. Video file and word file.	Action 7.1: The student provides feedback to his/her peers, self assesses his/her performance and indicates his/her commitments for the rest of the semester in the app.	None	Action 8.1: The student uploads team sketches and drawings produced during the conceptualization and idea generation stage. Pdf file.	None

Appendix C: Assessment activities per week

Act.	Wk 7	Wk 8	Wk 9	Wk 10	Wk 11	Wk12
Teaching staff actions	Action 4.2: Teaching staff uploads file. Word file.	Action 5.2: Teaching staff uploads report, reframing the problem feedback. Word file.	Action 6.2: Teaching staff grades the deliverable in the app.	Action 7.2: Teaching staff reviews student feedback to his/her peers and his/her commitments in the app.	None	Action 8.2: The teaching staff provides feedback on sketches and drawings produced during the conceptualization and idea generation stage in the app.
Act.	Wk13	Wk 14	Wk 15	End		
Student actions	Action 9.1: The student uploads the selection matrix, surveys to potential users, and low-resolution prototype pictures. Pdf file.	None	Action 10.1: The student must upload a video of his/her team oral presentation, and a report including process evidence, problem statement, generated ideas, selection matrix, surveys to potential users, analysis, low-resolution prototype, and peer and self - assessment. Video and pdf file.	None		

Appendix C: Assessment activities per week

Act.	Wk13	Wk 14	Wk 15	End
Action Teaching staff actions	None	Action 9.2: The teaching staff provides feedback on selection matrix, surveys to potential users, and low- resolution prototype pictures in the app.	None	Action10.2: Teaching staff grades the deliverable in the app.

Appendix D: Indicators per competence

Competence	Indicators
Oral Communication	The student orally expresses his/her opinions and learning in formal contexts, cautioning the use of time, diction and, eye contact with the audience.
Written Communication	The student writes reports that manage to integrate information collected from various authors and the experience of the observation phase, generating documents of their authorship.
Written Communication	The student describes the problem to be solved, using correctly the syntax defined for the course.
Written Communication	The student communicates the innovation process results, explaining the final solution features, the difficulties faced during the process, and how the team solved them implementing the tools taught in the course.
Teamwork	The student fulfills obligations and agreements, respecting the commitments acquired, in his/her academic activities and with the team.
Teamwork	The student expresses his/her opinions to the team clearly.
Teamwork	The student reviews his/her performance critically and provides constructive feedback to his/her peers.
Teamwork	The student organizes tasks, deadlines, and roles with which he/she commits.
Critical thinking	The student compares his/her previous beliefs, regarding an innovation challenge, with the visions of his/her peers and the collected evidence.
Competence	Indicators
Critical thinking	The student utilizes the necessary instruments to implement the field phase, applying data capture and recording techniques.
Critical thinking	The student inquiries about antecedents associated with an innovation challenge or need, using the suggested bibliography.
Critical thinking	The student interprets the information gathered from an ethnographic approach, managing to understand a need or challenge.
Critical thinking	The student describes the problem to be solved correctly, using the syntax defined for the course and reframe it according to the recommendations made by the teaching staff and the team's analysis.
Critical thinking	The student defines hierarchical attributes of a solution at a conceptual level linked to usability and user experience on product performance.

Appendix D: Indicators per competence

Critical thinking	The student communicates a conceptual solution to the innovation challenge, using a correct syntax, the user needs, and the reframed attributes in hierarchical order.
Critical thinking	The student utilizes diverse techniques to systematize his/her solutions to the innovation challenge.
Critical thinking	The student detects mistakes and achievements during the design process, analyzing the causes to extrapolate possible future improvements.

Appendix E: Summative and formative assessment process to be implemented in the application.

